

Transformational Leadership Behavior of School Heads and Teachers' Working Patterns of Public Elementary School

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Abstract. The study determined the extent of transformational leadership of school heads and the extent of teachers' working patterns of public elementary school. This study employed non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-correlation method. Validated questionnaire and Universal sampling procedure were utilized considering the minimal number of teachers in the research locale. One hundred twenty (120) public elementary school teachers were the respondents of the study. Using mean, pearson-r, and regression analysis, the findings revealed that the extent of transformational leadership of school heads was extensive while the extent of teachers' working patterns of public elementary school was also very extensive. Moreover, the overall results disclosed that indicators for transformational leadership of school heads have a strong positive relationship to the teachers' working patterns of public elementary school. Further, results from the regression analysis revealed the following have a strong influence of transformational leadership of school heads on teachers' working patterns of public elementary school: Providing Intellectual Stimulation, Fostering Commitment to Group Goals, Providing Vision and Inspiration, and Providing Individual Support. It was recommended that both school heads and teachers play essential roles in transforming a school's culture and improving educational outcomes. Collaboration, communication, and a commitment to ongoing growth are key elements for success in this endeavor.

KEY WORDS

1. Transformational leadership 2. teachers' working patterns 3. Intellectual Stimulation

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1. Introduction

Transformational leaders encourage their employees to grow professionally and meet a high standard of performance and productivity. Although this can help employees find value in their work and work hard toward goals, emphasizing balance may reduce the potential for burnout among employees. Transformational leaders create a climate in which the team members feel involved and important. It gives them the strength to work tirelessly towards the vision of the organization. Every leader lays down a clear vision for their organization to work on and makes them see that the vision is reachable. Likewise, the educational transformation perspective management success prevails a systematic change in educational model. It distinguishes innovation transformation of education in maintaining the model of educational management system and leadership. It reforms traditional teaching and substance learning pro-

cess structure of educational organization. It stresses educational transformation to determine sustainable strategy in educational leadership and management success in school organization. Transformational leadership helps transform members of a group into individuals who transcend beyond self-actualization and their own self-interests for the sake of the group or organization. Along with this includes individual moral development. First, transformational leadership might intrinsically foster more job satisfaction given its ability to impart a sense of mission and intellectual stimulation. Also, transformational leaders encourage the followers to take on more responsibility and autonomy. In the global perspectives, school heads transformational leadership has been characterized as superior leadership performance that occurs when leaders broaden, elevate the interests of their employees, generate awareness and acceptance of the purposes or mission of the group, and stir their employees to look beyond their own self-interest for the good of the group. This leadership stimulates and inspires followers to achieve beyond expectation and in the process developing their own capacities (Bass, 2020). The success of the organization depends not only on how the organization exploits its human capital and competencies but also on how it stimulates commitment to the organization (Nguni, 2016). The committed employees who are highly motivated to contribute their time and energy to the pursuit of organizational goals are increasingly acknowledged to be the primary asset available to an organization. Today's decentralization reforms are geared towards school restructuring, teachers' organizational commitment, job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior (Bogler, 2019). Gaining understanding of the way transformational leadership behavior influences these three teachers' work behavior and motivational aspect, is likely to enhance the prospect of school improvement. The ability to raise follower commitment is essential for a transformational leader to accomplish change, especially in uncertain times. Commitment creates greater individual productivity on behalf of the organization. Greater productivity allows the organization to meet its goals (Hay, 2016). Similarly, in the Philippines, in the Division of Biliran, reforms also need to be implemented due to the demands of the changing time, especially with the birth of the K to 12 Program. The reform initiative no doubt requires significant capacity development on the part of school administrators and teachers as well as stakeholders. It is along this premise that this study has been conducted to determine the extent of school heads' transformational leadership behaviors on teachers' working patterns in the Division of Biliran in terms of organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior and teachers' job satisfaction. Thus, results will shed great insights into the significant roles of administrators and teachers in carrying out quality education. Filipino leadership and management may appear to be misleading because Filipino culture is based on deeply ingrained indigenous core values. Filipino culture focuses on kinship, family, and social acceptance. Thus, Filipinos' distinct leadership styles may include pakiramdam, takutan, kulit, and patsamba-tsamba, among others. Filipino leadership styles have a significant effect in the workplace setting, as well as in schools and may significantly affect one's mental health. Franco (2017), in his study, identified the different Pinoy management styles that are distinctly Filipino. In Panabo City, school heads in any organization are expected to carry out tasks with limited resources to the maximum level to maintain the competitive edge and to sustain profitability position of the organization (Riaz, 2018). Leadership is the major element to preserve and improve an organization's competitive advantage over its competitor. It showed the stronger relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction. Organi-

zation must enhance job satisfaction among its workers to increase commitment. Said leader-

ship is a key factor of high job satisfaction thus increasing employee performance.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods, which give direction in this investigation. It includes the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures.

2.1. Research Design—This study used the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlational method. According to Bedo (2021), descriptive correlational method is used to determine the relationship between two or more variables and to ascertain their relationship. More to the point, Quilla (2021) emphasizes that this method is used since the study provides a description of individuals and aims to explain the nature of the data. This study is descriptive in nature since it assesses transformational leadership behavior of school heads and teachers' working patterns of public elementary school in Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. This is correlational since it determines transformational leadership behavior of school heads and teachers' working patterns of public elementary school.

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in seven (7) schools of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. The respondents were composed of 250-selected teachers of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. They have been in the service for at least five to ten years teaching experiences in the Department of Education (DepED) and have said something on the transformational leadership behavior of school heads and teachers' working patterns of public elementary school heads. Random sampling technique was employed in this study. However, Gredu Elementary School and Asuncion Elementary School with 100 percent of respondents were involved. For the rest of the schools, fifty percent were given the questionnaires. The schools

are equidistantly located in the whole district, which can be reached by means of land transportation facilities. The environment is conducive to educational research.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study adapted a questionnaire on transformational leadership behavior of school heads and was patterned and adapted by the researcher from Transformational Leadership Theory by Burns (1978) as cited by Enage, et. al., (2016). This theory promotes a style of guidance that emphasizes motivating employees and creating a vision and encouraging them to fulfill it. The fundamental skills of a transformational leader include being able to mobilize employees, inspire them and boost their morale. It based on the notion that certain leader behaviors transform followers' values, needs, preferences, and aspirations, and motivate them, "to perform above and beyond the call of duty. This is supported by Theory of Performance Bacon (2001) as cited by Ebio (2016). This theory is in the interaction between readers and text which enriches, extends, clarifies, and alters the interior and even the exterior lives of students. Teacher performance evaluation plays a key role in educational personnel reform, so it has been an important yet difficult issue in educational reform. The questionnaire was modified mainly through the researcher's preferences to suit the needs of the study. The adapted questionnaire was validated by the experts from the DepEd-Division of Davao City. Validity of the instrument ensured through expert's opinions and pilot testing. To ensure the reliability of the instru-

ment, a pilot test was conducted through calculating the value of Cronbach’s Alpha with the obtained values of 0.794. The questionnaire was divided into two (2) parts, school heads transformational leadership behavior and teachers working patterns of public of public elementary school. Hence, the Cronbach’s value of the construct has met the minimum reliability of 0.684, it means that the measures used are consistent enough for the study. In terms of instrument’s face validity, the items were modified to suit the purpose of this study and were validated by experts. The questionnaire was presented to the adviser for comments, corrections, and sugges-

tions. Part 1 of the questionnaire contained the items on transformational leadership behavior of school heads with the following providing vision or inspiration, modelling, fostering commitment to group goals, providing individual support, and providing intellectual stimulation. Part 2 pertained to the teachers’ working patterns of public elementary school with the dimensions, namely: organizational commitment, organizational citizenship, and job satisfaction. The perceptions of the respondents among the Panabo Central District teachers were based on the following Five-point Likert rating scales:

Range, Descriptive Equivalent, and Interpretation of Transformational Leadership Behavior of School Heads

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	The transformational leadership behavior of school heads is always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	The transformational leadership behavior of school heads is oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	The transformational leadership behavior of school heads is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	The transformational leadership behavior of school heads is rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	The transformational leadership behavior of school heads is not evident.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—1. Permission to conduct study. The researcher wrote a letter asking permission from the Dean of Graduate School to conduct this research study. The researcher secured a permit to conduct the study from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Panabo City through channels to the Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) of the different schools. 2. Distribution and retrieval of questionnaires. Upon approval of the permit to conduct the study, the sets of questionnaires were sent to the respondents via google forms

and through email-add of the school heads and teachers. The questionnaires were retrieved right after the respondents were through answering the questions and sent them back through researcher’s email-add or messenger. 3. Collection and statistical treatment of data. The data were collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time; therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in

Range, Descriptive Equivalent, and Interpretation of Teachers’ Working Patterns

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	Teachers’ working patterns is always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	Teachers’ working patterns is often-times evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	Teachers’ working patterns is some-times evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	Teachers’ working patterns is rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	Teachers’ working patterns is not evident.

the Philippine which was convened in January 2023. The collection of data was conducted following the protocols of IATF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. For some participants who were missed answering the questionnaire, the video call, via messenger,

viber, zoom or goggle meet were used to gather the data or responses of the participants. These were submitted to the statistician for analysis. The researcher together with the statistician tabulated the data, analyzed, and subjected them for statistical analysis.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study: Mean. It was used to determine the extent of transformational leadership behavior of school heads and teachers working patterns of public elementary school in Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r). This statistical tool was used in determining the significant compo-

nents of transformational leadership behavior of school heads and teachers working patterns of public elementary school heads in Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. Multiple Linear Regression. This was utilized to determine the significant of transformational leadership behavior of school heads influence teachers working patterns of public elementary in Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City.

3. Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter were the results of the data gathered. Two sets of research were employed to determine the extent of transformational leadership behavior of school heads and teachers’ working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. The discussion of the results and interpretations were presented accordingly based on the statement of the problems. Presentation of the interpretation was arranged according to the sub-headings: The extent of transformational leadership behavior of school heads in terms of providing vision and inspiration, modelling, fostering commitment to group goals, and providing individual support; the extent of teachers’ working patterns of public elementary school in terms of providing intellectual stimulation, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, and job

satisfaction; and which of the factors of transformational leadership behavior of school heads significantly influence the teachers' working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City.

Summary on the Extent of Transformational Leadership Behavior of School Heads. The summary information on the extent of transformational leadership behavior of school heads is reflected in table 1. The data are presented as follows: Providing intellectual stimulation has a mean of (4.21) with a description of very extensive. Then, it followed by providing individual support which gained a mean of (4.20) which also interpreted as very extensive. Likewise, modelling gained a mean of (4.19) which described as extensive. In addition, fostering commitment to group goals has revealed a mean of (4.17) or extensive. Finally, the respondents on providing vision and inspiration has generated a mean of (4.16) which also interpreted as extensive. It an overall generated mean of (4.18) or extensive, therefore the extent of transformational leadership behavior of school heads of public elementary school was extensive. This means that quality management of school heads improves learner and teacher performance.

Table 1. Summary on the Extent of School Heads Transformational Behavior

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Providing Vision and Inspiration	4.16	Extensive
2	Modelling	4.19	Extensive
3	Fostering Commitment to Group Goals	4.17	Extensive
4	Providing Individual Support	4.20	Very Extensive
5	Providing Intellectual Stimulation	4.21	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.18	Extensive

It can be gleaned from the table that providing vision and inspiration, modelling, and fostering commitment to group goals were extensive. Providing individual support and providing intellectual stimulation was the highest among the indicators of school heads transformational behavior of public elementary school. Kanat Maymon, et. al., (2020) discovered that the ability of transformational school head leaders to encourage their personnel to identify with the mission and vision of the organization had a favorable effect on teachers' autonomy motivation.

Summary on the Extent of Teachers' Working Patterns of Public Elementary School. Displayed in Table 2 are the data on the summary

on the extent of teachers' working patterns of public elementary school. The indicators are presented from highest to lowest mean ratings given by the respondents. Job Satisfaction has a mean of (4.23) with a description of very extensive. Then, it followed by organizational commitment has gained a mean of (4.20) which also interpreted as very extensive. Finally, the respondents find organizational citizenship behavior with a lowest mean of (4.19), which interpreted as extensive. It an overall generated mean of (4.21) or very extensive, therefore the extent of teachers' working patterns of public elementary school was very extensive. This meant that students would perform better academically at school as a result of the commitment, charac-

ter, and happiness displayed by teachers.

Table 2. Summary on the Extent of School Heads' Transformational Behavior

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Providing Vision and Inspiration	4.16	Extensive
2	Modelling	4.19	Extensive
3	Fostering Commitment to Group Goals	4.17	Extensive
4	Providing Individual Support	4.20	Very Extensive
5	Providing Intellectual Stimulation	4.21	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.18	Extensive

It can be gleaned from the table that organizational commitment and job satisfaction were very extensive. Organizational citizenship behavior was the least among the indicators of teachers' working patterns of public elementary school. Therefore, organizational citizenship behavior refers to people's acts that support efficient organizational operation. By providing a positive social and emotional environment in which the allocated task can be successfully completed, OCB accomplishes this efficiency and effectiveness. Because it fosters societal ties that influence how well employees perform at work, OCB is crucial for workers. The description and operation of the OCB have been discussed in numerous printed theoretical works, significant exploration, descriptive studies, revised volumes, and meta-analyses. The OCB is one of the most highly regarded topics in organizational behavior. This finding is congruent to the statement of Ocampo, et. al., and Newman, et. al., (2018), stating the success of a school depends on teachers' willingness to go above and beyond the call of duty in their volunteer positions. The behavior seen in educational environments differs from that seen in non-educational ones. Teachers who are generally dedicated to doing and providing the best for their organization oversee schools, which are service organizations. Individuals who engage

in organizational citizenship behavior go above and beyond the call of duty to fill an additional function for the organization.

Relationship Between the Transformational Leadership Behavior of School Heads and Teachers' Working Patterns of Public Elementary of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City

Shown in Table 3 is the statistical analysis on the significant relationship between the transformational leadership behavior of school heads and teachers' working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. Based on the analysis, the overall p-value is equal to 0.000 with an r-value equal to 0.563. This means that there is a weak positive significant correlation between the transformational leadership behavior of school heads and teachers' working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. Hence, this study rejects its established null hypothesis. The analysis further implies if there is an increase in the manifestation of transformational leadership behavior of school heads then it will lead to an increase also in the manifestation of teachers' working patterns of public elementary of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City.

Table 3. Relationship Between the Transformational Leadership Behavior of School Heads and Teachers' Working Patterns of Public Elementary School of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City

Transformational Leadership Behavior of School Heads	r	p-value	Decision on H ₀
Providing Vision and Inspiration	0.360	0.000	Reject
Modelling	0.110	0.082	Failed to Reject
Fostering Commitment to Group Goals	0.326	0.000	Reject
Providing Individual Support	0.522	0.000	Reject
Providing Intellectual Stimulation	0.535	0.000	Reject
Overall	0.563	0.000	Reject

Particularly, the analysis in the same table highlighted the relationship of each factor of the transformational leadership behavior of school heads and teachers' working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. The Providing Intellectual Stimulation factor of the school heads transformational leadership behavior ranked as the top indicator with a p-value of 0.000 and \neg r-value of 0.535. The numerical result implies that there is a moderate positive significant correlation between the providing intellectual stimulation factor and the teachers' working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. This was followed by the Providing Individual Support factor of the transformational leadership behavior of school heads obtaining a p-value of 0.000 and \neg r-value of 0.522. This means that there is a moderate positive significant correlation between the providing individual support factor and the teachers' working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. Next, the Providing Vision and Inspiration factor of the transformational leadership behavior of school heads obtained a p-value of 0.000 and \neg r-value of 0.360. This numerical analysis result means that there is a weak positive significant correlation between the providing vision and inspiration factor and the teachers' working patterns

of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. Lastly, the Fostering Commitment to Group Goals factor of the transformational leadership behavior of school heads obtained a p-value of 0.000 and \neg r-value of 0.326. Still, this numerical analysis result means that there is a weak positive significant correlation between the fostering commitment to group goals factor and the teachers' working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. On the other hand, the Modelling factor of the transformational leadership behavior of school heads obtained a p-value of 0.082 and \neg r-value of 0.110. This correlation numerical ratings are considered lower than its set critical value and higher than the set 0.05 alpha value. This means that there is no significant correlation between the modelling factor and the teachers' working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City.

Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of the Transformational Leadership Behavior of School Heads on the Teachers' Working Patterns of Public Elementary School of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City

Shown in table 4 is the regression analysis on the significant influence of the transformational leadership behavior of school heads on the teachers' working patterns of public elemen-

tary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. The overall regression analysis obtained p-value of 0.000 and F-value equal to 33.480 stating that transformational leadership behavior of school heads has a significant influence on the teachers' working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. This also implies that the regression model used in the analysis of the study is useful and that there is validity in the interpretation on the assumption of the said influences. Particularly, the said regression

analysis shows that four (4) out of the five (5) factors of the transformational leadership behavior of school heads significantly influenced the teachers' working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. Hence, the set null hypothesis of this study that there are no factors of the transformational leadership behavior of school heads that significantly influence the teachers' working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City.

Table 4. Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Transformational Leadership Behavior of School Heads on the Teachers' Working Patterns of Public Elementary School of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City

Teachers' Working Patterns	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	B	Std. Error	t	Sig.
Constant	2.717			12.609	.000	
Providing Vision and Inspiration	.098	.134	2.286	.043	2.286	.023
Modelling	.006	.007	.146	.038	.146	.884
Fostering Commitment to Group Goals	.095	.185	2.480	.038	2.480	.014
Providing Individual Support	.185	.443	5.951	.031	5.951	.000
Providing Intellectual Stimulation	.175	.352	6.067	.029	6.067	.000
R	0.638					
R²	0.407					
F-Value	33.480					
p-value	0.000					

Interpretation: Significant influence of providing vision and inspiration, fostering commitment to group goals, providing individual support, and providing intellectual stimulation on teachers' working patterns ($p < 0.05$).

Specifically, these school heads transformational leadership behavior factors in accordance to their t-test result value were the Providing Intellectual Stimulation factor which with an obtained t-value equal to 6.067 and a p-value equal to 0.000, the Fostering Commitment to Group Goals factor with an obtained t-value equal to 5.951 and a p-value equal to 0.000, the Fostering Commitment to Group Goals factor

with an obtained t-value equal to 2.480 and a p-value equal to 0.014, and lastly the Providing Vision and Inspiration factor with an obtained t-value equal to 2.286 and a p-value equal to 0.023. On the other hand, the Modelling factor of transformational leadership behavior of school heads does not significantly influence the teachers' working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of

Panabo City with a t-value equal to 0.146 and p-value equal to 0.884. This numerical rating is considered lower than its set critical value and higher than the set 0.05 alpha value. The regression analysis in the study resulted in an R-squared (R^2) value of 0.407, indicating that 40.7 percent of the variations in the transformational leadership behavior of school heads of public elementary school in Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City can be attributed to teachers' working patterns. In practical terms, this means that almost half of the effectiveness or style of leadership demonstrated by these school heads is influenced by how well they manage aspects directly related to their school's operations, goals, and stakeholder involvement.

Therefore, transformational leadership behavior of school heads emerges as a significant, albeit not exhaustive, determinant in shaping their leadership traits and effectiveness. Conversely, it is important to note that a significant 59.3 percent of the variability in transformational leadership behavior of school heads remains unexplained by teachers; working patterns alone, as per this study. This suggests that other factors, not explored in the current research, also play a substantial role in shaping the leadership qualities of school heads in Panabo Central District. These unidentified factors could range from personal characteristics like experience and training to broader organizational and community influences.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the findings of the study based on the data outcome. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher has laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—This non-experimental research using correlation design in this study aimed to determine the extent of transformational leadership behavior of school heads and teachers' working patterns of public elementary school. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the extent of school heads transformational behavior in terms of providing vision and inspiration, modelling, fostering commitment to group goals, providing individual support, and providing intellectual stimulation. Moreover, this identified the extent of teachers' working patterns of public elementary school in terms of organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, and job satisfaction. Finally, this study determined the significant relationship between the extent of transformational leadership behavior of school heads and the extent of teachers' working patterns of public elementary school. Using non-experimental research, the extent of transformational leadership

behavior of school heads and teachers' working patterns of public elementary school was determined. The respondents of the study were the 120-public elementary school teachers in Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. A modified teacher-made survey questionnaire was adopted from the study of Leadership Theory by Burns (1980) as cited by Engage, et al., (2019) and Theory of Performance of Bacon (2001) as cited by Ebio (2016) was utilized as the main instrument of this study. After thorough analysis, significant findings showed that the extent of transformational leadership behavior of school heads in terms providing vision and inspiration, modelling, fostering commitment to group, providing individual support, and providing intellectual stimulation was extensive. Similarly, the extent of teachers' working pattern of public elementary school in terms of organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, and job satisfaction was

extensive which means that it was always evident while in terms of transformational leadership behavior of school heads which is extensive. Hence, the extent of teachers' working patterns as demonstrated by public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City was very extensive. Based on the analysis, the overall p-value is equal to 0.000 with an r-value equal to 0.563. This means that there is a weak positive relationship between the transformational leadership behavior of school heads and teachers' working patterns of public elementary of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. Hence, this study rejects its established null hypothesis. The analysis further implies if there is an increase in the manifestation of transformational leadership behavior of school heads then it will lead to an increase also in the manifestation of teachers' working patterns of public elementary of Panabo Central District, Division of Panabo City. Finally, indicators of transformational leadership behavior of school heads such as providing vision and inspiration, fostering commitment to group goal, providing individual support, and providing intellectual support have significant influence of teachers' working patterns of public elementary school of Panabo Central District, Division of Davao City.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The transformational leadership behavior of school heads of public elementary school was extensive. The teachers' working patterns of public elementary school was also very extensive. There was a strong positive relationship between transformational leadership behavior

of school heads and teachers' working patterns of public elementary school based on the indicators. Based on the results revealed, the following indicators have a strong influence of transformational leadership behavior of school heads on the teachers' working patterns of public elementary school: Providing Vision and Inspiration, Fostering Commitment to Group Goal, Providing Individual Support, and Providing Intellectual Stimulation.

4.3. Recommendations—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: Transformational leaders inspire change by modeling the behavior they want to see in others. Demonstrate a strong work ethic, commitment to learners' success, and a passion for learning. Ensure that teachers have the necessary resources, training, and support to excel in their roles. Invest in professional development opportunities and provide mentoring or coaching when needed. Take advantage of professional development opportunities to enhance your skills and stay updated on the latest educational trends and research. Be open to trying new teaching methods and technologies. Embrace innovation to keep your teaching fresh and engaging. Both school heads and teachers play essential roles in transforming a school's culture and improving educational outcomes. Collaboration, communication, and a commitment to ongoing growth are key elements for success in this endeavor. Future Researchers may use the findings of this as springboard to conduct a study with a similar subject but with a larger scope to explore another dimension of the study

5. References

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